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Deliverable 2.3. Evaluation Outcomes and Sustainability Plans of CCLs

DATE OF DELIVERY - 31/03/2025

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DOCUMENT TRACKS DETAILS

Project acronym	SCORE
Project title	Smart Control of the Climate Resilience in European Coastal Cities
Starting date	01.07.2021
Duration	48 months
Call identifier	H2020-LC-CLA-2020-2
Grant Agreement No	101003534

Deliverable Information	
Deliverable number	Deliverable 2.3
Work package number	2
Deliverable title	Evaluation Outcomes and Sustainability Plans of CCLLs
Lead beneficiary	Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies (IHS)
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Due date	31/03/2025
Actual submission date	31/03/2025
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

VERSION MANAGEMENT

Revision table			
Version	Name	Date	Description
V 0.1	Enseñado, Elena Marie (IHS); Quadros Aniche, Laura (IHS); Nercua Wissink, Charmae (IHS)	20/02/2025	First draft
V 0.2	Riera-Spiegelhalter, Mar (ENT); Caruso, Rochelle	14/03/2025	Updated draft internally reviewed

	(ERINN); Borklund, Casey (ERINN); De Los Rios White, Marta (ENoLL); Makousiari, Elina (ENoLL); Soloaga, Sara (NAIDER)		
V 0.3	Enseñado, Elena Marie (IHS)	24/03/2025	Updated draft after contribution from partners
V1.0	Gharbia, Salem (ATU); Nalakurthi, Sudha-Rani (ATU)	31/03/2025	Final version

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
CCLL	Coastal City Living Lab
EBA	Ecosystem Based Adaptation
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
LL	Living Labs
MCA	Multiple Criteria Analysis
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
M&E	Monitoring and Evaluation
PM&E	Participatory Monitoring and Evaluation
SCORE	Smart Control of Climate Resilience in European Coastal Cities

BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE SCORE PROJECT

SCORE is a four-year EU-funded project aiming to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities.

The intensification of extreme weather events, coastal erosion and sea-level rise are major challenges to be urgently addressed by European coastal cities. The science behind these disruptive phenomena is complex, and advancing climate resilience requires progress in data acquisition, forecasting, and understanding of the potential risks and impacts for real-scenario interventions. The Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) supported by smart technologies has potential to increase climate resilience of European coastal cities; however, it is not yet adequately understood and coordinated at European level.

SCORE outlines a co-creation strategy, developed via a network of 10 coastal city 'Living Labs' (CCLs), to rapidly, equitably and sustainably enhance coastal city climate resilience through EBAs and sophisticated digital technologies.

The 10 coastal city Living Labs involved in the project are: Sligo and Dublin, Ireland; Barcelona/Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm and Basque Country, Spain; Oeiras, Portugal; Massa, Italy; Koper, Slovenia; Gdansk, Poland; Samsun, Turkey.

SCORE will establish an integrated coastal zone management framework for strengthening EBA and smart coastal city policies, creating European leadership in coastal city climate change adaptation in line with The Paris Agreement. It will provide innovative platforms to empower stakeholders' deployment of EBAs to increase climate resilience, business opportunities and financial sustainability of coastal cities.

The SCORE interdisciplinary team consists of 28 world-leading organisations from academia, local authorities, RPOs, and SMEs encompassing a wide range of skills including environmental science and policy, climate modelling, citizen and social science, data management, coastal management and engineering, security and technological aspects of smart sensing research.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the SCORE project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534.

The aim of this document, **Deliverable 2.3: Evaluation outcomes and sustainability plans of CCLs**, is to present the evaluation results of the CCL outcomes and the sustainability of the plans.

The evaluation strategy for the CCLs considered both the process (implementation) and the effect (outcome/impact). The process evaluation examined how activities were managed and implemented as intended, while the outcome evaluation captured the results and impacts within each CCL.

Led by IHS, there were three main activities under this task: (1) development of the evaluation strategy; (2) implementation of the evaluation activities; and (3) verification of the evaluation outcomes.

To develop the evaluation strategy, a framework was designed following a review of existing frameworks in the literature. This was followed by the validation of relevant themes, criteria, and indicators. These indicators were categorised into:

- Baseline assessment – Indicators relevant for an initial evaluation during the setup phase.
- Interim assessment – Indicators used to monitor CCLs as they progress through different phases and activities.
- Impact assessment – Indicators for the final evaluation of CCLs.

The evaluation activities were carried out through online survey questionnaires completed by each CCL at the end of each phase. The evaluation outcomes were then verified through online meetings and workshops, allowing CCLs to reflect on their processes, outcomes, and impacts while identifying areas for improvement. These workshops also supported the development of self-sustainability plans and provided feedback for continuous implementation.

The results of the CCL assessments are presented in this document, with findings from the comparative analysis used to assess the applicability and effectiveness of the Monitoring & Evaluation (M&E) framework.

LINKS WITH OTHER PROJECT ACTIVITIES

This deliverable is directly linked to **Task 2.7: Evaluation Strategy and Sustainability Plans of CCLLs** (Lead: IHS; Partners: NAIDER, ENoLL, ERINN, CCLL leaders; Month 7–Month 44).

Additionally, it is connected to the following tasks:

- Task 2.1: Designing the overall CCLL framework and methodology (Lead: ENoLL; Partners: IHS, NAIDER, ERINN, CCLL leaders; Month 1–Month 6).
- Task 2.2: Contextualizing the CCLL approach for each city (Lead: IHS; Partners: ENoLL, NAIDER, ERINN, CCLL leaders; Month 7–Month 12).
- Task 2.3: Preparation of the CCLL Pilot Operation Plans (Lead: NAIDER; Partners: IHS, ENoLL, ERINN, CCLL leaders; Month 7–Month 12).
- Task 2.4: Coordination and management of CCLLs (Lead: NAIDER; Partners: IHS, ENoLL, ERINN, CCLL leaders; Month 13–Month 38).
- Task 2.5: Implementing the Pilot Operation Plans in frontrunner CCLLs (Managing Lead: NAIDER; Operational Lead: CCLL leaders; Partners: IHS, ENoLL, ERINN; Month 13–Month 27).
- Task 2.6: Learning exchanges between frontrunner and follower CCLLs (Managing Lead: NAIDER; Operational Lead: CCLL leaders; Partners: IHS, ENoLL, ERINN; Month 28–Month 42).
- Task 2.8: Knowledge production and exchange (Lead: ERINN; Partners: IHS, ENoLL, ERINN, CCLLs; Month 6–Month 48).

Furthermore, this deliverable is connected to the following related deliverables:

- Deliverable 2.1: General Frontrunner CCLL Operation Plan (Lead: NAIDER; Month 12, Report - Confidential).
- Deliverable 2.2: General Follower CCLL Operation Plan (Lead: NAIDER; Month 27, Report - Confidential).
- Deliverable 2.4: CCLL Knowledge and Lessons Learned (Lead: ERINN; Month 47, Report - Public).

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1. INTRODUCTION

Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) are real-life, collaborative environments where diverse stakeholders co-create, test, implement, and evaluate solutions for climate resilience and adaptation. Within the SCORE project, the CCLL methodology follows a structured, four-phase approach: (1) Empathise & Define, where stakeholder needs and barriers related to climate resilience are identified; (2) Ideate & Co-Design, where stakeholders collaborate iteratively to develop a Minimal Viable Product (MVP); (3) Prototype & Pilot, where the MVP is tested in real-life settings through small-scale pilots; and (4) Test & Evaluate, where a broader feedback group assesses the solution's effectiveness and impact. This process ensures practical, community-driven solutions to enhance climate resilience. See Figure 1 for the CCLL methodology.

Figure 1 : CCLL methodology

Phase 1: Empathise & Define

Phase 1 serves as a diagnostic stage, assessing the city's current situation and defining the CCLL structure. The primary objective is to analyse the local context and identify key climate resilience challenges, stakeholder needs, and barriers. The insights gathered will guide the development and testing of solutions in later phases. Ultimately, this phase answers the critical questions: Why should the CCLL be established? Who should be involved?

Phase 2: Ideate & Co-Design

In this phase, stakeholders collaborate to define and design solutions for the problems identified in Phase 1. Using an iterative Minimum Viable Product (MVP) approach, the goal is to co-create feasible solutions that can be refined over time based on stakeholder feedback. This phase addresses the question: How should solutions be developed and refined?

Phase 3: Prototype & Pilot

Phase 3 focuses on implementing and testing the co-designed solutions in real-life settings. The developed solutions, following the MVP approach, undergo small-scale pilot projects to assess their applicability and

effectiveness in addressing the identified needs. Similar to Phase 2, this phase continues to explore how the CCLL can effectively address climate adaptation challenges in coastal cities.

Phase 4: Test & Evaluate

The final phase evaluates the solutions on a larger scale to ensure their effectiveness and broader applicability. This phase ensures that the developed solutions are not only effective but also scalable and sustainable for long-term climate resilience.

Figure 2 : Map of SCORE CCLLs

This deliverable outlines the evaluation strategy and sustainability plans for CCLLs. The framework is grounded in established monitoring and evaluation (M&E) approaches for Living Labs (LLs) and incorporates participatory monitoring and evaluation (PM&E) principles. It addresses both process (management and implementation) and effect (outcomes and impacts) through three core activities: developing the evaluation framework (methodology), implementing evaluation activities (data collection), and verifying outcomes (results).

Progress was assessed at each key phase through online surveys and meetings, facilitating reflection and improvements. Additionally, online workshops supported the development of sustainability plans to ensure the long-term self-sufficiency and effectiveness of the CCLLs. The M&E framework was applied across ten CCLLs within the SCORE project, which aims to enhance climate resilience in European coastal cities. Comparing its application across these ten CCLLs offers valuable insights for developing a universally applicable framework for M&E of CCLLs. See Figure 2 for the map of SCORE CCLLs.

2. MONITORING AND EVALUATION

Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) is a method used to achieve desired outcomes and assess the effects of interventions (Myrick, 2013). It evaluates whether results are reaching stakeholders, how they are achieved over time, and their actual outcomes and impacts. Consistent application of M&E supports learning and adaptation (Masuku et al., 2015). Participatory Monitoring and Evaluation (PM&E) expands on M&E by involving stakeholders in defining problems, planning, implementing, and evaluating interventions (Holte-McKenzie et al., 2006). This approach leverages local knowledge and empowers participants to assess needs and act on findings (Estrella & Gaventa, 1998).

In the context of CCLLs, PM&E is recognised as a core feature (Steen & van Bueren, 2017). Despite its importance, there is a notable gap in systematic frameworks for evaluating the impact of CCLLs. A universally accepted strategy is essential for measuring and evaluating CCLL processes' performance and broader impacts (Bronson et al., 2021; Ballon et al., 2018). PM&E adds critical value from the outset by establishing a baseline for assessing overall CCLL performance (Ravetz et al., 2018) and supports interim assessments to facilitate reflection, learning, and timely interventions for continuous improvement.

Developing and refining such evaluation frameworks is both scientifically and practically significant. Academically, these frameworks synthesise research findings into methodologies accessible to practitioners. Practically, they address the increasing adoption of LLs across diverse regions and sectors. From a societal perspective, standardised evaluation enhances citizen participation in innovation projects, strengthening democratic processes and the legitimacy of interventions.

A uniform evaluation framework would enable cross-project comparisons, providing insights into the contexts where LLs are most effective and impactful. Such an PM&E framework could also guide participants, particularly those unfamiliar with LL concepts, through the development, implementation, and evaluation phases. Beyond EU-funded initiatives, these frameworks could support the wider adoption of LLs by offering a structured and replicable implementation approach.

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodological approach consists of four steps. First, a literature review was conducted to identify criteria and indicators for the PM&E of the CCLLs. Second, these criteria and indicators were reviewed and validated by a group of academics, experts and practitioners, which resulted in deriving criteria clusters for the PM&E of CCLLs. Third, data were collected through survey questionnaires, complemented by online meetings with CCLLs. Fourth, the results were analysed using descriptive statistics and thematic analysis are presented. Finally, the findings from the comparative analysis were used to reflect on the applicability and effectiveness of the M&E framework.

3.1. Literature review

The literature review yielded 14 different evaluation frameworks for CCLLs. See Table 1 for the list of evaluation frameworks reviewed. Each framework was analysed according to its description, variables, possible indicators, measurement units, data collection methods and data analysis used. The results were synthesised into preliminary indicator clusters. The process was iterative and involved cross-checking with the original literature to ensure coherency. The indicators were divided into baseline assessment, interim assessment, and impact

assessment. The category baseline assessment includes all indicators that are relevant for a preliminary evaluation of the CCLL during the setup phase. The interim assessment includes indicators relevant for monitoring the CCLLs as they go through the different phases and activities, while the impact assessment covers the final evaluation of the CCLLs.

Table 1: List of evaluation frameworks reviewed

	Authors	Name of evaluation frameworks
1	Maculiene and Skarzauskeine (2020)	Digital Co-creation Index framework for Evaluation in EU
2	Ondiek and Moturi (2019)	The four-capital method of sustainable development evaluation
3	Dell'era and Landoni (2019)	Conceptual framework mixing user centered strategy and participatory strategy
4	Ballon, et al. (2018)	Logical effect model Living Labs
5	Osorio, et al. (2019)	Maturity grid-based assessment tool
6	Kovacs (2016)	Harmonisation cube
7	Mastelic, et al. (2015)	Business model canvas
8	Veeckman et al. (2013)	Living lab triangle conceptual framework
9	Guzman et al. (2015)	Process reference model
10	Stahlborst et al. (2012)	Key principles to guide evaluation processes in LL
11	Chen & Chou (2010)	Living lab analysis model
12	Vontas & Protogeris (2009)	Evaluation toolkit
13	Parkinson & Ramiraz (2007)	The sustainable livelihood model
14	Geenhuizen (2018)	Living Labs as boundary spanners

3.2. Strategy Validation

Once the list of criteria clusters and respective key indicators was outlined, we validated the strategy internally, externally and with the CCLLs. Firstly, an internal review of the strategy was performed by 14 members of the SCORE project consortium. For the internal review, project consortium members working on the design, implementation, and evaluation of the CCLLs were individually asked to perform the following instructions. In the first step, each indicator was examined in terms of the questions, measurement units, data sources, data instruments, and frequency for data collection. In the second step, each indicator was assessed based on five criteria, indicating whether the indicator is specific, measurable, realistic, attainable, and relevant by choosing 'yes' or 'no'.

Here specificity refers to the indicator's ability to be clear and focused to avoid ambiguity. Measurability refers to the ability to be quantified either qualitatively or quantitatively. Realistic meaning that the indicator can be measured regularly in a cost-effective way and within the timeframe of the project. Attainability concerns the indicator's ability to be achieved and validated under any circumstances. Relevancy concerns whether the indicator is relevant for SCORE and the CCLLs. In the third step, each colleague was asked to suggest whether to retain, remove, or improve

the key indicators. Afterwards, the results of the validation process were synthesised, and the list of key indicators was reformulated accordingly.

Secondly, an external review via a public webinar was performed. During the public webinar, attendees were first asked background questions, such as: ‘What is your level of knowledge on the evaluation of LLs? ‘What is your level of experience on the evaluation of LLs? These were followed by pertinent questions, such as: ‘Which components of the LLs should be evaluated?’, ‘What are the most important metrics for evaluating LLs?’ and ‘Who should evaluate LLs?’.

Thirdly, validation of the LL evaluation strategy happened through the online meetings with the CCLLs wherein they were asked for their review and feedback. Similarly, an earlier survey also revealed what the CCLL’s level of knowledge and experience on the evaluation of LLs including which components and metrics to be evaluated and who should evaluate. Further, final indicators for the impact assessment were drawn from the European Network of Labs'Living Labs (ENoLL) harmonised framework (Vervoort, et al., 2022). The main themes and indicators for the baseline, interim, and impact assessment as outlined below.

Baseline assessment

Ten (10) major themes, including key indicators, comprise the baseline assessment of the CCLLs. See Table 2 for the list of major themes and key indicators for the baseline assessment.

Table 2 : List of major themes and key indicators for the baseline assessment

	Major Themes	Key Indicators
1	Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of objectives and vision for the CCLL • Definition of the scope of the CCLL (subject matter and physical context)
2	Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of financial, human, time & material resources
3	Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of roles and responsibilities in the management of the CCLL • Identification of relevant stakeholders for the CCLL
4	Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of knowledge and experience of LL concept and methodology
5	Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existence of (previous) collaboration and innovation activities in the city / CCLL
6	Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of stakeholder and user involvement in the CCLL
7	Solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existence of (previous) solutions that are relevant for the CCLL • Identification of problems to be addressed by the CCLL • Identification of potential barriers for the success of the CCLL
8	Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge and experience of participatory tools relevant to the different phases
9	Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequency of internal and external communication • Definition of a communication strategy for the CCLL

10	Knowledge sharing / learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of relevant knowledge for the CCLL • Existence of partnerships and networks where knowledge is shared
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Interim assessment

Three (3) major themes and key indicators were also defined for the interim assessment. Interim assessment relates to the key phases, namely Phase 1: Empathise and define; Phase 2: Ideate and co-design; Phase 3: Prototype and pilot; and Phase 4: Test and evaluate. See Table 3 for the list of major themes and key indicators for the interim assessment of the CCLLs.

Table 3 : List of major themes and key indicators for the interim assessment

	Major Themes	Key Indicators
1	Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vision and plan of the core team
2	Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders involved in the CCLL
3	Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Over-all satisfaction • Level of satisfaction with content • Level of satisfaction with results • Quality of over-all engagement process
4	Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usefulness of different tools (e.g., SWOT analysis, Fishbone analysis, Force Field analysis, Stakeholder Mapping; Canvas; Stakeholder List)

Endline assessment

The endline assessment, which was based on ENOLL's Harmonized Living Lab Evaluation Framework (Vervoort, et al., 2022), is comprised of six chapters (or themes) and 15 criteria of sustainable Living Labs.

Figure 3 : Harmonized Living Lab Evaluation Framework (Vervoort, et al., 2022)

See Table 4 for the list of major themes, criteria, and key indicators for endline assessment of the CCLLs.

Table 4 : List of major themes, criteria, and key indicators for the endline assessment (Authors)

Major Themes	Criteria	Key Indicators
1 Strategy	Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A well-defined and shared vision and mission for the Living Lab, based on real identified needs of quadruple helix actors Involvement of actors of the quadruple helix on a strategic level Clearly defined roles and responsibilities within the Living Lab governance team A clear strategy roadmap, including the expected impacts of the Living Lab strategy and the Living Lab projects
	Business Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A view on the business plan of the Living Lab A well-defined and described service portfolio for various phases of innovation and collaboration processes
	Culture and collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proof of connections/interest to connect with external (regional/national/ international) innovation ecosystems Smart and adaptive cooperation/collaboration within the Living Lab design to build trust Quality of the internal communication processes Channels and tools within the Living Lab to build trust
2 Operations	Human resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability of qualified staff Assignment of qualified staff to different roles and responsibilities

		Operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Running and finished Living Lab projects Monitoring processes for operational aspects of the Living Lab Open innovation project management Status of the Living Lab in general
		Equipment and infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allocation of necessary Living Lab equipment and infrastructures (e.g., software, hardware, spaces) to the Living Lab team Availability of necessary Living Lab equipment and infrastructures (e.g., software, hardware, spaces) to the Living Lab team, indicated in time (from continuous to rarely)
3	Openness	Innovation partnerships, projects, and processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reflective and iterative approach of the Living Lab Ethical approach of the Living Lab Openness towards new partners and investors Presence of the necessary transparent data agreements between the Living Lab and its partners, stakeholders, and users Level of transparency of the Living Lab
		Ownership of results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feedback protection Shared vs. Formal ownership Intellectual property (IP) processes
4	Users and reality	User-centricity of the user and stakeholder engagement approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Description and intensity of the user participation User impact on the innovation process Amount of actively involved users in the Living Lab activities
		Quality of the iterative Living Lab processes in real-life contexts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adoption of an iterative Living Lab methodology in the user engagement approach Involvement of users in real life contexts (e.g., at home, work, in the public space)
		Appropriateness of the participatory tools and methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engagement strategies to match evolving needs of users Range of used tools and methods Quality and innovativeness of tools and methods to involve users in the different steps of the iterative Living Lab process
5	Impact and Value	Co-created values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> User and stakeholder satisfaction (e.g., influence on the process, capacity building) Degree of knowledge exchange among Living Lab stakeholders (e.g. Community platform, knowledge hub) Academic validation for researchers (e.g., publications) Capacity building for/by network actors (e.g., learning materials, trainings)
		Impact of the Living Lab	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring of impacts

6	Stability and harmonization	Stability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Societal impact (e.g., behavioural change, inclusion, diversity, digital gap) • Economic impact (e.g., patents, market disruption, speed of market penetration, decrease of cost) • Environmental impact (e.g., reduction of pollution, increase of air quality) • Regulatory impact (e.g., public policies, regulations) • Technological impact (e.g., increase TRL levels of technologies)
		Harmonization and scale-up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of financial sustainability based on a balanced and diversified set of fundings and revenue streams • Strength of partnerships • Degree of network collaboration
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardization of Living Lab procedures, processes, tools, methods and technologies • Replication of Living Lab processes, tools, methods, infrastructures and solutions • Cross-sectoral and geographical collaboration

3.3. Data collection

Data collection was conducted through online survey questionnaires, supplemented by online meetings and workshops with CCLLs. The baseline assessment was conducted with all 10 CCLL teams in two rounds—first in January 2021 and then between April and May 2022—to establish an initial understanding of the context and conditions. The interim assessment was conducted for all the four phases in different periods with participation of CCLL team members and stakeholders. For the endline assessment, all CCLLs completed the survey between July and August 2024. Additionally, online sustainability planning workshops were conducted from September to November 2024. The primary goal of these workshops was to enable CCLLs to develop self-sustainability plans and receive feedback for continuous implementation.

	Activity	Participants	Period
1	Baseline Assessment	All 10 CCLL teams	January 2021; April-May 2022
2	Interim Assessment: Phase 1	29 CCLL team members and 25 CCLL stakeholders	April – May 2022; December 2022
3	Interim Assessment: Phase 2	23 CCLL team members and 45 CCLL stakeholders	March – July 2024
	Interim Assessment: Phase 3	12 CCLL team members and 2 CCLL stakeholders	March – July 2024
4	Endline Assessment	All 10 CCLL teams	July – August 2024

5	Online sustainability workshops	All 10 CCLL teams	September – November 2024
6	Interim Assessment: Phase 4	11 CCLL team members	December 2024

Baseline assessment

For the baseline assessment survey that was distributed to all 10 CCLLs, the questionnaire contained statements that can be assessed in a 5-point Likert scale format for a uniformly quantifiable comparison of all CCLLs. The respondents were asked to rate the questions with the likert scale 1-5: (1) strongly disagree – or – insufficient; (2) disagree – or – not good; (3) nor agree nor disagree – or – neutral; (4) agree – or - sufficient; and (5) strongly agree – or – excellent. Furthermore, respondents were invited to give additional remarks connected to the statements. See Table 5 for the list of survey questionnaire statements for the baseline assessment.

Table 5 : List of survey questionnaire statements for the baseline assessment

	Themes	Survey Questionnaire Statements
1	Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The objectives and vision of the CCLL are identified. The scope of the CCLL (subject matter and physical context) is defined.
2	Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The financial resources and support were sufficient to achieve the goals set out for year one. There are/will be sufficient financial resources and support in achieving the coming goals in year two. There were enough people and participants in your CCLL to achieve the goals of year one. There are/will be enough people and participants working in your CCLL to achieve the goals of year two. The time the core team spent on SCORE/the CCLL was sufficient to achieve the goals of year one. The core team has sufficient time to spend on SCORE/the CCLL to achieve the goals of year two. The material resources in your CCLL were sufficient to achieve the goals of year one. There are/will be sufficient material resources to achieve the goals of year two.
3	Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The roles and responsibilities of the CCLL core team are clearly defined and understood. The stakeholders involved in the CCLL are well-identified.
4	Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There were/are already collaboration and innovation activities taking place in your city/CCLL related to coastal resilience. Collaboration or innovation activities for year two of SCORE are already defined and planned.
5	Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholders were already involved or engaged during year one of SCORE. There is a plan on how to involve stakeholders in year two of SCORE.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users/citizens were already involved or engaged during year one of SCORE. • There is a plan on how to involve users/citizens in year two of SCORE.
6	Solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical solutions to address coastal resilience were implemented in the past in your city. • The main problems to be addressed by the CCLL are identified. • Potential barriers that could hamper the success of the CCLL are identified.
7	Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The team has sufficient knowledge of participatory tools relevant to the different phases • The team has sufficient experience in using participatory tools relevant to the different phases • The CCLL core team has the necessary tools to start activities in the CCLL.
8	Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There was frequent internal communication among the CCLL core team during year one of SCORE. • The CCLL core team has a plan on how to communicate (internally) for year two of SCORE. • There was frequent external communication between the CCLL core team and stakeholders during year one. • The CCLL core team has a plan on how to communicate externally with stakeholders for year two of SCORE.
9	Process ¹ / Knowledge Learning/ Sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The CCLL core team has a plan on how to communicate externally with stakeholders for year two of SCORE. • The CCLL core team is part of network(s) where knowledge is shared on LLs, ecosystem-based adaptation, and smart technologies, among others. • What is your level of experience with LLs? • What is your level of knowledge on LLs? • What is your level of knowledge on co-design? • What is your level of experience in co-design? • What is your level of knowledge on Testing & Prototyping at LLs? • What is your level of experience on Testing & Prototyping at LLs? • What is your level of knowledge on the evaluation of LLs? • What is your level of experience on the evaluation of LLs? • What is your level of knowledge on implementing LLs? • What is your level of experience in implementing LLs? • What is your level of knowledge on replicating and scaling-up LLs? • What is your level of experience on replicating and scaling-up LLs?

¹ Key indicators under process (Level of knowledge and experience of LL concept and methodology) have been combined with key indicators under knowledge learning / sharing (Availability of relevant knowledge for the CCLL; existence of partnerships and networks where knowledge is shared).

Interim assessment

For the interim assessment, two (2) survey questionnaires were prepared: one for CCLL team members and one for CCLL stakeholders. Likewise, a likert scale of 1-5 was used and that respondents were asked to provide relevant remarks. See Table 6 for the list of survey questionnaire statements for the interim assessment for CCLL team members and stakeholders.

Table 6 : List of survey questionnaire statements for the interim assessment

	Themes	Survey Questionnaire Statements
1	Organization	Vision and plan of the core team : For CCLL team members <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Our CCLL core team has a clear vision for our CCLL. • Our CCLL core team feels more confident to run our CCLL following the workshop. • Our CCLL core team has the adequate skillsets to run our CCLL. • Our CCLL core team feels ownership over our CCLL and its future. • Our CCLL core team understands what a CCLL is. • Our CCLL core team can confidently explain the CCLL concept to non-experts. • Our CCLL core team has a clear plan for our next steps in the 6-12 months. • Our role(s) as a frontrunner and/or follower are clear.
2	Stakeholders	Stakeholders involved in the CCLL : For CCLL team members <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The stakeholders at the workshop were able to provide relevant inputs for the CCLL's development. • There were essential stakeholder groups missing from the workshop.
3	Process	For CCLL team members and stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rate the over-all level of satisfaction with the (CCLL workshop) specific phase. • Rate the level of satisfaction with the content of the (CCLL workshop) specific phase. • Rate the level of satisfaction with the results of the (CCLL workshop) specific phase.
		For CCLL stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please rate the quality of your overall engagement process with your CCLL.
4	Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usefulness of different tools (e.g., SWOT analysis, Fishbone analysis, Force Field analysis, Stakeholder Mapping; Canvas; Stakeholder List)

Endline Assessment

The survey questionnaire for the endline assessment includes open questions, multiple choice questions, and rating of statements ranging from 'currently missing' (not implemented/operational within the LL at this moment), 'planned for' (still under development, including partly implemented processes), to 'in place' (fully

implemented/operational within the LL). See Table 7 for the list of survey questionnaire statements and questions for the endline assessment for CCLL team members.

Table 7 : List of survey questionnaire statements and questions for the endline assessment

	Themes	Survey Questionnaire Statements and Questions
1	Stability and harmonization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How many partners have joined or left the managing group/governance team of your organization/Living Lab over the last 3 years? • Which types of Living Lab services, tools, methods and/or Living Lab infrastructures developed by your organization/Living Lab have been replicated by partners of the managing group/governance team of your organization/Living Lab over the last 3 years? • Which types of Living Lab services, tools, methods and/or Living Lab infrastructures developed by your organization/Living Lab have been replicated by other Living Lab (networks) over the last 3 years? • Looking at the overall finances of your organization (Living Lab), approximately what % of revenues are provided by different funding streams? • What kind of other revenues are provided to your living lab? • For how long are these different revenue streams secured? • Over the last 3 years, has your Living Lab been involved in projects and/or initiatives in which multiple Living Labs, cross-border/cross-sector, collaborate, using harmonised Living Lab processes, tools, methods and/or infrastructures?
2	Impact and value	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How many times per year does your Living Lab share information, knowledge and results with its users/ participants and external stakeholders? • Which types of learning materials (capacity building) has your Living Lab produced for different types of stakeholders over the last 3 years? • Does your Living Lab have methods in place to monitor the satisfaction of users and/or stakeholders concerning their involvement/influence on the innovation cycle and concerning knowledge sharing and capacity building? Does your organization/Living Lab use standardised methods and forms to monitor the satisfaction of users and/or stakeholders across different Living Lab projects and activities? • How frequently are the different types of impact of the Living Lab monitored by internal self-monitoring impact assessment processes beyond the scope of an individual Living Lab project?
3	Users and reality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which different types of stakeholders from your ecosystem are participating as users in Living Lab projects and/or activities over the last 3 years? • In general, within your Living Lab, to what extent can users/participants in your Living Lab projects exert influence on the different phases of the Living Lab innovation cycle? • How regularly does your organization/Living Lab involve users/participants in their real-life context within the current Living

		<p>Lab projects of your Living Lab? Which of the participatory tools and methods are used by your organization/Living Lab?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In which phases of the Living Lab innovation cycle is your Living Lab/organization using these participatory tools and methods?
4	Openness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How is your Living Lab safeguarding a reflective and iterative approach to (transdisciplinary) collaboration? • How is your Living Lab safeguarding an ethical approach to (transdisciplinary) collaboration? • How is your Living Lab implementing the required processes regarding the use, sharing and licensing of data and IP of collaborative outcomes? • Which of the following are integrated into the user agreements your Living Lab is signing with every individual user of its projects?
5	Operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which internal roles, expressed in allocated working time (FTE), have been allocated to run the Living Lab operations? • How many Living Lab projects has your Living Lab completed over the last 3 years? • How much time (in person months) was allocated to running and/or participating in these projects? • How frequently are the internal components of the Living Lab followed up by the managing team/ governance team through self-monitoring processes? How frequently are the equipment and infrastructure of your Living Lab accessible to the Living Lab team to be used?
6	Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which different types of stakeholder groups of the quadruple helix are present in the ecosystem of your Living Lab? • To what degree are the strategic parts implemented/planned for in your Living Lab? • What types of stakeholders are actively involved in the development of the vision and mission of the Living Lab and the governance structure of the Living Lab? • How frequently does the managing group/governance team of the Living Lab organises meetings to monitor the progress of the Living Lab and make strategic decisions? • How frequently does the Living Lab internally share strategic decisions, information about upcoming actions, and results of past projects/activities, beyond the scope of an individual Living Lab project, with their strategic partners and Living Lab staff? • Which of the elements are currently present in the business model of your Living Lab? • For which of the different steps of the Living Lab innovation cycle is your Living Lab offering Living Lab services to its customers? • Which types of management processes are in place in your Living Lab? • With how many individual Living Labs or other innovation networks has your Living Lab been actively collaborating over the last 3 years on a local, regional, national, or international scale beyond the scope of one individual Living Lab project?

3.4. Data analysis

After collecting the data, the results were analysed using a mixed-methods approach. Descriptive statistics were applied to the quantitative data to summarize and quantify key patterns, trends, and distributions across responses. In parallel, thematic analysis was employed to examine the qualitative data, allowing for the identification and interpretation of recurring themes, perspectives, and insights. This qualitative analysis added depth and context to the quantitative findings, offering a more comprehensive understanding of the data.

4. RESULTS

The results section is divided into three parts: baseline, interim, endline assessment, and sustainability plans.

4.1. Baseline assessment

Overall evaluation

The baseline assessment results show that *Objectives* (4.1), *Resources* (3.8), and *Organization* (4.0) received the highest scores, indicating that the CCLLs have a well-defined vision, structured resource allocation, and clearly established roles and responsibilities. These strengths suggest a solid foundation for project implementation. However, *Activities* (3.3) and *Participants* (3.4) scored lower, reflecting potential challenges in engagement, collaboration, and stakeholder involvement. While *Solutions* (3.8) and *Tools* (3.6) indicate moderate preparedness, there is room for improvement in implementation and practical application.

Figure 4: Results per main theme for the baseline assessment

Communication (3.7) is relatively strong, signifying effective interactions, but *Knowledge* (2.0) received the lowest rating, highlighting a critical gap in expertise related to co-design, testing, and evaluation of the CCLLs. To enhance CCLL effectiveness, capacity-building programs, stronger stakeholder participation, and refined collaborative strategies should be prioritised, ensuring that the initiative not only maintains its structural strengths but also

strengthens expertise and engagement in the long term. See Table 8 for the results per evaluation criteria per main theme for the baseline assessment.

Table 8 : Results per evaluation criteria per main theme for the baseline assessment

	Main Themes	Criteria	Sub-Scores	Average
1	Objectives	Objectives and vision Scope and context	4.1 4.1	4.1
2	Resources	Financial Resources (Year One) Financial Resources (Year Two) Participants (Year One) Participants (Year Two) Core Team Time (Year One) Core Team Time (Year Two) Material Resources (Year One) Material Resources (Year Two)	4.2 3.5 3.9 3.3 3.9 3.5 4.1 3.5	3.8
3	Organization	Roles & Responsibilities Stakeholder Identification	4.0 3.9	4.0
4	Activities	Existing Collaboration & Innovation Planned Collaboration & Innovation (Year Two)	3.2 3.4	3.3
5	Participants	Stakeholder Engagement (Year One) Stakeholder Engagement Plan (Year Two) User/Citizen Engagement (Year One) User/Citizen Engagement Plan (Year Two)	3.5 3.7 2.7 3.6	3.4
6	Solutions	Past Technical Solutions Problem Identification Barrier Identification	3.2 4.3 4.0	3.8
7	Tools	Participatory Tools Knowledge Participatory Tools Experience Availability of Tools	3.7 3.2 3.9	3.6
8	Communication	Internal Communication (Year One) Internal Communication Plan (Year Two) External Communication (Year One) External Communication Plan (Year Two)	4.1 3.8 3.3 3.5	3.7
9	Process/ Knowledge Sharing/ Learning	Knowledge-Sharing Networks LL Experience Level LL Knowledge Level Co-Design Knowledge Co-Design Experience Testing & Prototyping Knowledge Testing & Prototyping Experience LL Evaluation Knowledge LL Evaluation Experience LL Implementation Knowledge LL Implementation Experience LL Replication & Scaling Knowledge LL Replication & Scaling Experience	3.1 1.7 2.3 2.4 2.0 2.0 1.8 2.0 1.7 2.0 1.6 2.0 1.4	2.0

4.2. Interim assessment

Overall evaluation

Organization

In terms of the vision and plan of the core CCLL team, results have shown steady improvement across phases, with notable gains in clarity of roles, vision, and communication. The teams have developed a stronger structure and strategic direction, as reflected in their increased confidence in explaining the CCLL concept and a better understanding of its purpose. While skillset adequacy stabilised, indicating a consistent level of competency, some areas remain unchanged or fluctuating. The sense of ownership over the CCLL has not improved, suggesting a need for stronger leadership engagement and responsibility. Additionally, confidence levels and clarity of planning have varied, pointing to periodic uncertainties in execution. Moving forward, sustaining clarity in planning, enhancing leadership involvement, and reinforcing ownership will be key to ensuring long-term success.

Figure 5 : Rating on the vision and plan of the CCLLs

Stakeholders

Stakeholder engagement has steadily improved over time, with an increase in meaningful contributions and a decline in missing stakeholder groups. While involvement peaked in Phase 3, there was a slight decline in Phase 4, indicating that while engagement has strengthened, there is still room for further integration of diverse perspectives. The number of missing stakeholder groups has gradually decreased, reflecting successful inclusivity efforts, though gaps remain. Industry and Civil Society have consistently been the most frequently absent groups, with Government also missing in some instances, particularly during CCLL workshops and the sensor selection process. By Phase 4, Industry remained the most absent group, highlighting the need for continued outreach efforts to strengthen representation and diversity. Moving forward, targeted strategies should focus on actively involving Industry, Civil Society, and Government representatives to ensure a comprehensive and balanced stakeholder network within the CCLL.

Figure 6 : Stakeholders involved in the CCLLs

Process

The CCLL Team Members' satisfaction followed a rising trend until Phase 3, with notable improvements in results, content, and overall satisfaction. This peak suggests that engagement, clarity, and effectiveness were at their highest during this phase. However, in Phase 4, the satisfaction metrics dropped slightly, returning to levels similar to earlier phases. This decline, particularly in satisfaction with results and overall satisfaction, suggests that while the team remained engaged, the impact of discussions and outcomes may not have been as strong as in the previous phase. Despite this, content satisfaction remained relatively high, indicating that materials and discussions were still well-received.

Figure 7 : Process satisfaction by the CCLLs' Team Members

For CCLL Stakeholders, the quality of overall engagement and content satisfaction followed a similar trend, peaking in Phase 3 after a decline in Phase 2. The satisfaction with results dropped in Phase 2 and only slightly recovered in Phase 3, indicating that while engagement and content delivery improved, stakeholders may not have been entirely satisfied with the workshop outcomes. The overall satisfaction remained relatively stable, suggesting that

the stakeholder experience remained generally positive. Moving forward, maintaining high engagement and refining the clarity and effectiveness of outcomes will be key to ensuring sustained satisfaction among both team members and stakeholders. Unfortunately, inputs from stakeholders on Phase 4 were not collected – which was a limitation for this deliverable.

Figure 8 : Process satisfaction by the CCLL Stakeholders

The following sections highlight the different phases, showcasing success stories, key achievements, areas for improvement, expanded initiatives, and upcoming plans, among others.

Phase 1: Empathise and Define

Success Stories: Key Highlights and Achievements

The activities under this phase were highly successful for both team members and stakeholders, thanks to their clear structure, well-organised activities, and engaging methodologies. Strong guidance and explanations helped clarify project objectives and priorities, while interactive communication fostered collaboration among stakeholders from various sectors, including academia, citizens, administration, and businesses. The tools and materials provided effectively supported brainstorming, stakeholder engagement, and problem-solving, leading to a shared understanding of the project. See Table 9 for the rating of the usefulness of the different tools. The workshops also helped strengthen team relationships and commitment, while diverse perspectives encouraged innovative ideas, particularly in discussions on climate change warning systems. Stakeholders valued the opportunity to meet partners in person, exchange ideas, and deepen their understanding of the CCLL concept. The combination of structured activities, interdisciplinary collaboration, and interactive sessions made the workshops both informative and inspiring, ensuring strong stakeholder involvement and teamwork throughout the process.

Table 9 : Rating of the usefulness of the different tools under Phase 1

	Tools	Average
1	SWOT Analysis Tool	4.4
2	Fishbone Analysis Tool	4.3
3	Force Field Analysis Tool	4.2

4	Stakeholder Mapping Tool	4.5
5	Canvas	4.1
6	Stakeholder List	4.5
7	Pilot Operational Plan	4.1

Improvements Needed: Areas for Growth and Future Considerations

Key areas for improvement in the activities include broadening stakeholder engagement, refining workshop structure and timing, and enhancing communication strategies. Expanding participation to include more diverse stakeholders, such as the general public, and ensuring clearer invitations, interactive activities, and simplified language would improve accessibility. Many participants suggested shortening online presentations, making sessions more concise, and adjusting schedules to accommodate cultural and professional differences. A better balance between theoretical discussions and practical exercises was also recommended to increase engagement. Additionally, stakeholders highlighted the need for clearer identification of key participants, better inclusion of affected groups, and more interactive, hands-on sessions. Ensuring pre-workshop preparation and aligning content with stakeholder interests would enhance participation. Shortening sessions, optimizing schedules, and sharing previous results were also suggested to maintain engagement and prevent fatigue. Overall, refining stakeholder integration, improving content delivery, and optimizing workshop duration will help create more effective and engaging workshops in the future.

Participants provided mixed feedback on workshop outcomes and follow-up, with some expressing uncertainty about results and emphasising the need for a clear summary of all sessions to benefit those unable to attend. Collaboration and international engagement were seen as valuable, with suggestions to host workshops in different countries to broaden participation and impact. Some participants appreciated the opportunity to represent their organizations and contribute to discussions, while others highlighted the need for better pre-workshop coordination, proposing preliminary meetings among regional project partners to improve preparation and alignment. Overall, while the collaborative environment was well-received, there is room for improvement in communication, pre-workshop planning, and expanding international participation to enhance future workshops.

Expanded Initiatives: Activities and Results

While most participants did not engage in additional activities beyond scheduled activities, some took part in internal focus meetings, research efforts, site visits, and follow-up planning. These initiatives aimed to define roles, apply concepts in real settings, and strengthen stakeholder engagement through further discussions with key groups and the public.

Phase 2: Ideate and Co-Design

Success Stories: Key Highlights and Achievements

The CCLL activities under this phase were highly successful, with strong stakeholder participation, effective organization, and meaningful knowledge exchange. Attendees actively engaged in discussions, particularly on Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) of Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA), leading to valuable feedback and collaboration between stakeholders and SCORE partners. See Table 10 for the rating of the usefulness of the different tools under Phase 2. The well-structured sessions facilitated brainstorming, stakeholder role identification, and policy planning for the next 6-12 months, including policy briefs and interviews. The workshops were well-organised, with clear presentations, expert facilitators, and strong support from local authorities, ensuring smooth coordination. Stakeholders appreciated the interactive discussions, structured voting process, and balance between formal and informal engagement, which fostered a dynamic and collaborative atmosphere. Overall, the workshops effectively

enhanced stakeholder involvement, knowledge sharing, and strategic planning, making them a valuable and impactful experience for all participants.

Table 10 : Rating of the usefulness of the different tools under Phase 2

	Tools	Average
1	Stakeholder Mapping Tool	4.1
2	Stakeholder Journey Tool	3.9
3	Power-Interest Matrix Tool	3.9
4	Multiple Criteria Analysis	4.1
5	Strategy Development and Value Importance Tool	3.9

Improvements Needed: Areas for Growth and Future Considerations

The CCLL activities could be improved by enhancing stakeholder engagement, workshop structure, and clarity of information. A more balanced representation of civil society, local government, and the private sector is needed, as some sessions were dominated by academics or the SCORE project team members, limiting diverse perspectives. Better pre-workshop preparation, including background materials and clearer explanations of key concepts like EBAs and MCA, would help stakeholders engage more effectively. Workshop formats and logistics require adjustments, such as optimizing room setups for discussions, refining voting processes, and improving survey methods to better accommodate participants. Additionally, stakeholders emphasised the need for more technical assessments to evaluate proposed measures, clearer distinctions between expert and general discussions, and improved scheduling—such as holding sessions in the evening—to encourage broader participation. Refining terminology explanations, stakeholder briefings, and time management would also enhance engagement. Lastly, ensuring the full alignment and involvement of the CCLL team, creating synergies between stakeholders, and adapting methodologies to local contexts would make the workshops more inclusive, impactful, and effectively structured for future success.

Expanded Initiatives: Activities and Results

Several CCLLs have conducted additional activities beyond the ones planned under this phase, including stakeholder engagement, technical meetings, educational initiatives, and field visits. Meetings with universities, local governments, and industry representatives have focused on sensor selection, project development, and stakeholder collaboration. Educational outreach and citizen engagement have been key priorities, with workshops at science fairs, schools, and universities aimed at raising awareness and encouraging participation in citizen science initiatives. Field visits and hands-on activities, such as sensor installation and environmental monitoring, have also contributed to CCLL development, with some teams supporting municipalities in technical aspects of sensor deployment. However, challenges like the absence of key stakeholders due to external factors, such as extreme weather events, have occasionally limited the scope of activities. Despite this, many CCLLs have successfully mobilised local actors, particularly through science clubs and institutional partnerships, strengthening collaboration and technical advancements in environmental monitoring and climate resilience efforts.

Upcoming Plans: Next Steps and Objectives

Several CCLLs planned to deepen stakeholder engagement through follow-up meetings, interviews, and bilateral discussions, addressing key topics from previous workshops. Recognizing accessibility challenges, some teams aim to engage more local groups in their own settings rather than university-based events. Citizen science and public engagement remain priorities, with initiatives such as interview surveys, community-driven environmental projects,

and participation in major conferences. Certain teams will focus on data collection and technical discussions, including bilateral meetings for models and other data needs, while others plan to expand private sector involvement through face-to-face visits. Additionally, some CCLLs are exploring synergies with other projects, particularly within H2020 and municipal initiatives, to enhance collaboration and resource-sharing. Overall, the activities aimed to strengthen stakeholder participation, refine technical data collection, and foster cross-project collaboration, ensuring a more inclusive and effective CCLL development process.

Stakeholder Interests: Key Topics and Activities for Future Engagement

Stakeholders expressed strong interest in a variety of technical, environmental, and community engagement activities within the CCLL after this phase. Many highlighted the need for local mapping and sensor-based monitoring, particularly for sea level rise, river level changes, erosion, and human impact on dunes, along with expert advice on dune management and invasive species control. Others emphasised the importance of economic evaluations and financial risk assessments related to climate adaptation, as well as citizen science initiatives and biodiversity-related activities. Training sessions and multi-stakeholder workshops were frequently requested, alongside progress updates and partial results from the project. There was significant interest in sensor selection, installation, and community-driven data collection, with mentions of using tools like Minecraft and participation in Green Week events. Overall, stakeholders showed enthusiasm for hands-on activities, stakeholder-inclusive discussions, and educational sessions that blend technical insights with local community engagement. Positive feedback emphasised the value of multidisciplinary collaboration, the relevance of the topics discussed, and a strong willingness to stay involved in future initiatives.

Phase 3: Prototype and Pilot

Success Stories: Key Highlights and Achievements

The sensor selection workshop was highly successful, with clear objectives, strong organization, and active stakeholder engagement. Participants appreciated the structured presentations, which effectively outlined sensor deployment goals, and the use of interactive digital tools like GeoSurvey, which facilitated feedback collection and dynamic discussions. Stakeholders, students, and educators actively participated, contributing high-quality proposals and meaningful exchanges. A major success was the delivery of weather stations to educators, along with a handbook of activities to integrate them into academic curricula, which was well-received and easy to implement. The sensor catalogue was also valued as a useful decision-making resource. See Table 11 for the rating of the usefulness of the different tools under Phase 3. Additionally, the group-based approach encouraged collaboration, and insights from participants with prior experience enriched the decision-making process. Overall, the workshop was well-structured, informative, and interactive, providing clear takeaways for sensor selection and deployment.

Table 11 : Rating of the usefulness of the different tools under Phase 3

	Tools	Average
1	Catalogue Sensors (CCLL team members)	4.5
2	Catalogue Sensors (CCLL stakeholders)	2.0
3	GeoSurvey (CCLL stakeholders)	2.0

Improvements Needed: Areas for Growth and Future Considerations

While the sensor selection workshop was well-received, several areas for improvement were identified, including extending the workshop duration to allow for more in-depth discussions and stakeholder engagement. Participants

highlighted the need for more background information on existing sensor data and detailed technical insights to enhance decision-making. Stakeholder follow-up was another key area, with recommendations to provide a summary of workshop outcomes and an online version for those unable to attend in person. Additionally, citizen engagement strategies for water level measurement sensors need to be carefully planned to maximise public participation and awareness. Stakeholders also suggested restructuring the sensor placement approach by first defining objectives before determining locations, ensuring better alignment with project goals. Overall, improving workshop duration, technical information, stakeholder follow-up, and engagement strategies would make future sensor selection workshops more effective and impactful.

Expanded Initiatives: Activities and Results

Several CCLLs conducted additional activities beyond the sensor selection workshop, though a notable number of respondents reported no further involvement. These activities included technical meetings to finalise sensor types, determine placement locations, and assess physical and network conditions such as coverage and authorization requirements. Community engagement was a key focus, with informal meetings involving local government staff and community representatives to discuss sensor selection and deployment. Some CCLLs also organised public presentations of selected sensors, engaging stakeholders, municipalities, and local media to raise awareness. Additionally, citizen science initiatives were launched, particularly in Oeiras, where local school science clubs participated in environmental monitoring efforts. Public outreach efforts also included a "Week of Nature" initiative, where children and youth learned about early warning systems and sensors through interactive sessions, such as a Lego workshop. Overall, these activities strengthened stakeholder collaboration, increased community awareness, and advanced the technical groundwork for sensor deployment.

Upcoming Plans: Next Steps and Objectives

Several CCLLs planned to conduct follow-up activities to further engage stakeholders and refine sensor deployment. A key focus is on collecting feedback, including sending follow-up emails with a preliminary list of sensors for stakeholder input and holding small meetings with individual stakeholders to discuss sensor installation and management. Efforts were also underway to evaluate synergies with other projects, particularly H2020 initiatives and municipal programs in Oeiras, to enhance collaboration and resource efficiency. Public engagement remains a priority, with planned workshops targeting different audiences, including a session with municipal representatives from neighbouring cities on sensor deployment strategies, a citizen workshop on EBA measures, and a follow-up survey to assess changes in citizen awareness of climate change since Green Week 2023. Additionally, CCLL core teams considered new events in collaboration with the municipality and stakeholders to strengthen engagement and showcase progress.

Stakeholder Interests: Key Topics and Activities for Future Engagement

Participants expressed interest in sensor selection activities related to bathing water quality, with a particular focus on the technical aspects of sensor implementation and data collection.

Phase 4: Test and Evaluate

Success Stories: Key Highlights and Achievements

The online sustainability planning workshops were well-received, with strengths in interactive discussions, knowledge exchange, and structured organization. See Table 12 for the rating of the usefulness of the different tools under Phase 4. Participants appreciated the breakout discussions, which enabled the exchange of views, experiences, and lessons learned among CCLLs. The structured agenda and well-chosen topics led to dynamic discussions, allowing teams to gain insights from mature Living Labs and compare approaches across different CCLLs, helping them identify weaknesses and refine future objectives. The workshops fostered a positive atmosphere, promoting collaboration

and problem-solving, while the final session summaries helped consolidate key takeaways and reinforce important lessons. Overall, the workshops effectively facilitated knowledge transfer, strategic planning, and meaningful stakeholder interactions for advancing sustainability initiatives.

Table 12 : Rating of the usefulness of the different tools under Phase 4

	Tools	Average
1	Self-Assessment Survey	3.7
2	Sustainability Planning Workshops	4.4

Improvements Needed: Areas for Growth and Future Considerations

While the sustainability workshops were well-received, several areas for improvement were identified. Participants suggested inviting external experts to provide fresh insights and introducing short breaks to maintain engagement. Some felt that topics were repetitive, with overlapping discussions across sessions, and recommended structured moderation to keep conversations focused. Additionally, incorporating more hands-on activities, practical demonstrations, and diverse case studies would better illustrate real-world applications of sustainability strategies. While breakout sessions encouraged internal discussions within CCLs, some participants felt they limited cross-learning between cities. A balanced approach that allows for both internal reflections and broader exchanges could enhance the learning experience. Overall, refining session structure, increasing practical engagement, and incorporating external perspectives would further improve the effectiveness of future sustainability workshops.

Expanded Initiatives: Activities and Results

While some CCLs have conducted additional activities, the majority reported no further initiatives beyond the recent sustainability workshops. However, certain CCLs engaged in stakeholder-focused and internal activities to strengthen collaboration and refine sustainability strategies. These included working groups addressing cultural heritage and water scarcity, onsite meetings and discussions on EBAs, internal meetings to align sustainability strategies among members, and knowledge transfer sessions between and among CCLs. Additionally, an online workshop for Sligo County Council helped share results with local authorities, supporting informed decision-making. These activities have enhanced stakeholder engagement, clarified long-term sustainability plans, and improved communication within the CCL network.

Upcoming Plans: Next Steps and Objectives

While some participants have no immediate plans, others have outlined key activities focused on funding, stakeholder engagement, environmental education, and long-term sustainability. Several CCLs aim to develop new projects for funding to support ongoing working groups and sustainability initiatives. Others plan to conduct stakeholder meetings and collaborate with city councils to install sensors and implement EBAs, such as sand dune restoration. Environmental education efforts will continue, particularly through school engagement to raise awareness among younger generations. Additionally, documentation and knowledge-sharing initiatives are planned, including a summary report for CCL Oeiras, detailing key activities and lessons learned from the SCORE project. To ensure long-term impact, some teams are also focused on sustaining awareness efforts, particularly in alignment with the SCORE Training School Year 3 (2025). Overall, these activities emphasise implementation, stakeholder collaboration, sustainability, and knowledge dissemination beyond the project's completion.

4.3. Endline Assessment

Overall evaluation

The survey results reveal that most of the main themes are near the average, ranging from 32/100 to 51/100, while *Users & Reality* went above average with 60/100. This reflects the emphasis on collaboration with users, the level of engagement of stakeholders, as well as the quality of participatory methods and tools. The theme that scored the least was *Value & Impact*, with 30/100, showing that not only developing co-created values (such as knowledge sharing, capacity building, and network building) is important, but also how these diverse (social, environmental, etc.) generated impacts are monitored. See Figure 9 for the results per main theme.

Figure 9 : Results per main theme for the endline assessment

The results per evaluation criteria revealed that the majority of the 10 CCLs performed the best in the following areas: *Tools & Methods* (71,25); *User-centricity* (65,17), *Equipment & Infrastructure* (62,14), and *Business Model* (58,13). See Figure 10 for the results per evaluation criteria per main theme.

Figure 10 : Results per evaluation criteria per main theme for the endline assessment

However, most CCLs scored significantly lower in the following aspects: *Ownership of Results* (20,187), *Impact* (21,87), *Stability* (21,94), *Operations* (30,56), and *Co-Created Values* (35,50). See Figure 4 for the results per evaluation criteria.

Figure 11 : Results per evaluation criteria for the endline assessment

4.4. Sustainability Plans

The sustainability planning workshop results showed that most CCLs have achieved significant project outcomes, both tangible and intangible. These achievements were strongly linked to the CCLs' efforts in fostering strong relationships with partners and key stakeholders, allowing them to effectively share and mainstream their results within the wider community.

Key co-created values—such as EBAs, sensors, digital twins, ICT platforms, and stakeholder engagement—have played a crucial role in demonstrating the network's technological advancements while driving societal and environmental impact within cities.

The long-term sustainability of CCLs and their co-created values depends on reinforcing and maintaining these relationships, while also expanding the network's financial and human resources. Additionally, the CCLs highlighted that having a clear and shared vision and objectives from the outset of network-building is essential for ensuring both its sustainability and long-term stability.

The CCLL model has proven effective in fostering long-term engagement on climate issues, as demonstrated by some of the CCLs which have successfully secured funding to sustain their networks' activities and initiatives.

The sustainability workshops created a valuable platform for the 10 CCLs to share experiences, exchange best practices, and learn from one another on overcoming common challenges and barriers to achieving self-reliance and long-term sustainability. Throughout the sessions, CCLs received constructive peer feedback on strategies to address these challenges effectively. For a detailed overview of the CCLs' plans and strategies for addressing sustainability challenges, see Table 13 below.

Table 13 : Overview of CCLL challenges and way forward actions and strategies

Criteria	Key challenges	Way forward actions and strategies
Co-created values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Co-creation is inherently complex and challenging ▪ Limited resources (time, money & people) which limits ability to focus on co-creation activity ▪ Size and diversity of stakeholders pose challenges i.e. varying levels of knowledge, limited availability, different priorities ▪ Difficult to maintain consistent engagement with the same stakeholders over a long period. ▪ Visibility of results and real effects from co-created actions needs longer time to be seen. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Strengthening relationships built within the CCLL in its co-created actions by providing access to key stakeholders who are vital for promoting activities and building trust i.e. nurturing local CCLL champions. ✓ Strengthen ties between CCLL core partners and focusing on the CCLL as a unified entity ✓ Maintain and establish new agreements between core partners ✓ Expand the CCLL team by identifying and engaging key stakeholders for ongoing involvement ✓ Ensure sustained funding and continuity given that most of the challenges relate to resources
Operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Geographical distance between partners and key stakeholders poses challenges in implementing activities ▪ Limited resource availability including budget constraints ▪ Legal regulations and red tape hinder CCLLs actions/activities ▪ Heavy administrative workloads and time management ▪ Identifying the right collaborators and determining the best ways to engage them ▪ Stakeholder engagement is time-consuming and challenging 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Seek support and engage in meaningful collaborations. Encourage team members to actively seek opportunities within the community. ✓ CCLL take the time to reflect on progress made. Taking the time to debrief can enhance the CCLLs function, efficiency and alignment of objectives. ✓ Explore ways to improve CCLL's management and governance ✓ Identify any missing skills within the team and try to fill the skills gap within the CCLL team. ✓ CCLLs also take the time to celebrate successes.
Impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Getting commitment and continual monitoring with stakeholders is difficult due to time constraints and technological literacy ▪ Monitoring technological results i.e. smart sensors, digital twins, EBAs are quite easy but it is still challenging to measure the impact that these results bring to society and the planet. ▪ A challenge to extend beyond the academic and technological impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Explore and/or strengthen collaborative monitoring between municipality and the academic funding. ✓ Increase awareness and engagement in the community for behavioral impacts i.e. monitor through surveys and workshops. ✓ Assessment of the implementation of policy recommendations ✓ For technological impact, CCLLs plan to look at the baseline/ end of

	<p>(which CCLLs have higher results) to a more societal and regulatory impact.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Taking data/results and translating these into policy is challenging for most CCLLs. A few CCLLs managed to incorporate some results to local climate actions plans. 	<p>SCORE monitoring to measure tangible impact.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ CCLLs consider assigning a person (s) responsible for the impact assessment and creation of these processes. This correlate with better funding.
Ownership of Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ There is a significant amount of co-created results the CCLLs have achieved and although dissemination is a continuous work, it remains to be a challenge especially to specific target groups like the policy makers and the public. ▪ Making results accessible to stakeholders to keep them engaged is still difficult. A huge barrier is sharing results in a simplified terminology as well as translating it in the local language. ▪ It takes time to build trust in the community, policy makers and the public for projects like SCORE. Significant achievements have already been done by the CCLLs when it comes to sharing and co-creating results and this needs to be maintained. ▪ Most CCLLs faced political and legal barriers in utilizing the SCORE project results. ▪ Mainstreaming results to be brought into practice in the municipality level remains a challenge for most of CCLLs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Maintain and strengthen the relationships with partners and stakeholders that are already built within the project to collectively share co-created results and mainstream these results to city level implementation. ✓ Ensure to share CCLL results in an accessible way e.g. simplified terminology, local translation and appropriate communication channels.
Stability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ For most CCLLs, securing funding and human resources for current and future activities is still one difficult challenge to address towards stability and sustainability of the network. ▪ Most CCLL achieved results by focusing on people and relationships specifically building trust within the key partners. The major challenge of the CCLLs is how to maintain and nurture these relationships to be able to maximise the project results to deliver societal and environmental impacts to their respective cities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Nurturing the relationships built within the CCLL team, with key stakeholders and within the wider community will be the focus in the last months of the SCORE project and even beyond the project. ✓ Utilise the community of Living Labs established within SCORE to continue the work even beyond the project as well as leveraging the CCLL project results to secure funding for continued network activities.

- For most CCLLs, there is a continuous need to have a strong governing and management structure for stability and harmonization of activities within the network.
- Having the right and diverse set of skills within the CCLL team are also needed for sustainability of the network.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The CCLL framework under the SCORE project effectively integrates a structured four-phase methodology to develop and test climate resilience solutions through stakeholder collaboration and iterative evaluation. The M&E framework ensures structured assessment as the absence of a standardised evaluation framework limits cross-project learning and scalability. The M&E framework however can be improved further and applied in similar projects.

The CCLL data collection process combined online surveys, meetings, and workshops to enable a structured assessment across baseline, interim, and endline phases. Likert-scale questionnaires provided quantifiable comparisons, while written feedback added contextual insights. Discussing survey results individually with each CCLL further enriched the evaluation. To improve efficiency, reducing time gaps between surveys and activities through online feedback sessions would enhance recall and data accuracy. Standardizing stakeholder participation is also critical to ensure consistent and unbiased results.

To enhance tracking and knowledge-sharing, introducing a “journey diary”—a structured document for logging activities, challenges, and key developments—would help CCLLs monitor their progress. Additionally, a shared online platform, such as Miro or an online dashboard, could improve visibility and collaboration across CCLLs. As data collection evolves, new evaluation themes should be integrated, focusing on continued commitment and future CCLL support. These improvements will ensure a more dynamic, transparent, and effective M&E process.

The baseline assessment highlighted strong foundational elements in objectives, resources, and organization, suggesting a well-structured framework for project implementation. Communication was also relatively robust, indicating effective interaction mechanisms. However, lower scores in activities and participants suggested challenges in engagement and collaboration, while knowledge emerged as a critical weakness, reflecting gaps in expertise related to co-design, testing, and evaluation. To enhance effectiveness, efforts focused on capacity building, stakeholder participation, and refining collaborative strategies to strengthen expertise and engagement for long-term success.

The interim assessment of the CCLLs highlighted significant progress in organization, stakeholder engagement, and project execution. Improvements were observed in the vision, strategic direction, and communication of CCLL core teams, with increased confidence in explaining the CCLL concept. Stakeholder involvement also grew, peaking in Phase 3, though engagement slightly declined in Phase 4, particularly among Industry, Civil Society, and Government representatives, signaling a need for targeted outreach and inclusivity efforts. Despite strong participation, satisfaction with outcomes varied, with Phase 3 receiving the highest ratings, while uncertainties in leadership engagement and planning clarity remained ongoing concerns. While the sustainability planning workshops were well-

received, challenges persist in maintaining engagement, securing funding, and translating project results into policy actions.

To ensure long-term sustainability and impact, CCLLs must focus on strengthening leadership accountability, expanding stakeholder participation, and securing diversified funding sources. Better pre-workshop preparation, structured moderation, and integrating external expertise can improve stakeholder engagement. Developing clear governance structures, refining impact assessment strategies, and fostering cross-sector collaboration will be key to embedding CCLLs into policies. Additionally, enhanced knowledge-sharing mechanisms, policy integration, and continuous stakeholder involvement will help ensure that the CCLLs remain effective and scalable beyond the SCORE project's duration.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to all CCLL team members and stakeholders from Sligo and Dublin, Ireland; Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm and Oarsoaldea, Spain; Oeiras, Portugal; Massa, Italy; Koper, Slovenia; Gdansk, Poland; and Samsun, Turkey. Additionally, we extend our appreciation to the SCORE project consortium members and external reviewers who participated in the strategy validation process, providing valuable insights and feedback. We also acknowledge the invaluable contributions of former SCORE project colleagues in developing the methodology, collecting data, and analysing results. Special thanks go to Vicens i Roig, Eudald (IHS); Kammerer, Lukas (IHS); Den Dekker, Janneke (IHS); Lionggo, Indriany (IHS); Aamot, Tiril (IHS); Vanelli, Francesca (IHS); Vervoort, Koen (ENOLL); Undabeitia Paz, Asier (NAIDER); and Anton, Iulia (ATU) for their dedication and support in shaping this research.

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